

**EDUCATE YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM
ANCESTORS IN THE PROCESS**

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Abstract: *This article deals with patriotism and its main criteria in the development of young people as patriots, with a special emphasis on patriotism in the education system.*

Keywords: *patriotism, people, education, national education system, patriotism.*

Independence ushered in a period of great changes in the history of our Motherland, inspired millions of people to believe in their own strength, and paved the way for people's initiatives. Independence has established a social order that allows the realization of creative thoughts and feelings hidden in man. Thanks to independence, we have taken our destiny, our army, into our own hands. Our ancestors have always fought valiantly for the freedom and independence of the Motherland. We must pay attention to the social, economic and political situation in Central Asia in the early XI century, the escalation of the struggle in Movarounnahr in the last stages of Mongol oppression, the struggle between Genghis Khan and its consequences, the actions of the Sarbadars, the conditions of Amir Temur's arrival in Movarounnahr.

It should be noted that the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan need to create a fast, well-equipped, well-equipped military sector capable of effectively and reliably protecting the peace and tranquility of our country.

The military reforms being carried out in our Armed Forces have set before us a wide-ranging and very responsible task. To solve them, we need high intelligence and strength, in our large and complex military mechanism we need to further

improve the organization and discipline at all levels, strengthen the leadership and improve the leadership of the troops, maximize combat readiness in units and divisions. should.

"Education and upbringing, their whole meaning is to constantly conquer the abstraction, to strive to know more and more"

(Emel Zolya)

It is known from historical traditions and experiences that education has always been based on the policies and goals of a particular society and system.

As the great thinker Avloni emphasized, "Education is for us a matter of life, or death, or salvation, or destruction, or happiness, or disaster." It is clear from it that man integrates upbringing from life, nature and society. Man came to life, fights for life, and life nurtures him.

The great scholar Abu Abdullah Rudaki, the founder of Tajik literature in the 11th century, said:

While upbringing has a strong connection with education, it also has its own laws. Education and upbringing is a unique process. But they are not exactly alike. The unity of education and upbringing, first of all, in the whole pedagogical process, which consists of the commonality of their purpose, education always performs educational functions, and upbringing plays a responsible role, such as knowing life and preparing for it.

The great commander, the enlightened scholar Abu Nasir Farobi in his work "Classification of Sciences" called "arithmetic, geometry, astronomy and music as educational science . " Because young people are brought up because of them. These sciences make our youth more delicate. "It will be difficult to master the sciences of nature without mastering the so-called educational sciences." "Education is formed only through words and teaching, and education is carried out through practical work and experience," he said.

In determining the goal of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, the requirements of society, the breath of the times, national characteristics are taken as a basis. The purpose of education is to cultivate a perfect human personality that is fully developed in all respects. Based on these goals, the military team and each soldier determine the tasks of educational work, determine its content, and the Commanders choose the forms and methods of training military personnel, taking into account the working conditions.

While the main task of military education is to arm soldiers with knowledge, in education the military is to form the moral skills and abilities, needs and aspirations

of the faith in accordance with the rules of ethics adopted in military schools, in our society.

Abdulla Avloni, an Uzbek folk pedagogue and educator, emphasized the role of education in human development in his book "Turkish Gulistan" or "Ethics" ; " Mr. Truth has created human beings to be gifted and talented, to distinguish between good and evil, good and bad, white and black. But the development of human ability is through education. If a child grows up with a good upbringing, avoiding corrupt behavior, and becoming accustomed to good behavior, everyone will turn out to be an acceptable, happy person. If he grows up without morals, he will become an ignorant, ignorant, disgraceful world who does all kinds of depraved things and does not listen to advice. Educators are like a doctor, just as a doctor treats a sick person's body, so the educator must make the child's anger center bigger by giving him a cure for "good behavior" out of a cure for "good behavior." We have been commanded to correct our behavior according to the commandments, but the main claw for our good behavior is upbringing. Upbringing has a great influence on the beauty and beauty of our moral building. "

According to the Shari'a, it is obligatory for fathers to bring up their children well, and it is obligatory for fathers to bring up orphaned children of their own nation.

Since the dawn of mankind, people have been engaged in the upbringing of children in one form or another. At that time, this process was sometimes consciously and sometimes unconsciously. They have acquired a deeper and broader meaning as a result of the passage of time, the complexity of life and life.

Human basically two way with education tipishi possible .

1. Someone 's directly effect , ie teach , as well as the wise ideas , advice and works through reading ;
2. Human own think , people behavior , did and doing from work appropriate conclusions take out get the most powerful-thinking and through upbringing possible ;

Your child growth and upbringing his activity in the process instead is increased . Education give deganda scientist fuzalolar only to the child education give they understand . In our opinion , this understanding otherwise depending on upbringing only children not adults both attractive we can do need.

